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Development of Self-Government of Teachers in the Cultural and Educational Space of the Multi-Ethnic Region (on the Example of the Khabarovsk Territory)

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Abstract

The paper presents the experience of cluster interaction in the cultural and educational space of the Khabarovsk Territory, built on the principles of interaction between institutions of preschool, general, secondary vocational and higher education for the exchange of experience and the dissemination of best practices for the development of ethnocultural competence and the linguistic culture of the personality of students. The presented pedagogical system contributes to the creation of conditions for the development of personal self-government of future teachers at the stages before university and postgraduate education.

Keywords: cultural and educational space, personal self-government, cultural intelligence, basic beliefs, educational cluster.

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Introduction

Today, in the current situation of the development of Russia, the importance of taking into account regional specifics in the field of education is increasingly manifested (Bagdasarova, 2008). The Khabarovsk region is home to about 145 nationalities, representatives of various linguistic groups and ethnic communities in the all-Russian cultural space is a multi-ethnic, multi-religious, multicultural region. As a result, against this background, certain contradictions in the interethnic sphere may arise, having not only socio-political, economic, but also spiritual foundations, manifested in cultural and value differences (Astashova et al., 2018; Bagdasarova, 2008; Gozhev, 2004).

As a result, the education system of the Khabarovsk Territory provides for a set of measures to strengthen the training of teachers, including improving the quality of training of graduates for teaching in the multicultural environment of the Far Eastern region. So, one of the priority areas of the state program «Development of Education in the Khabarovsk Territory» (State program of the Khabarovsk Territory «Development of Education in the Khabarovsk Territory», 2020) is to improve the quality of professional education, the development of mechanisms for continuing teacher education, as well as bringing the structure of professional education in line with the needs of innovative development of the economy of the region.

Considering these aspects, since 2013, the Resource Center «Multicultural Education Ethnocultural Development of Personality» has been established on the basis of the Federal Autonomous Educational Institution of Higher Professional Education «Far Eastern State Humanitarian University» (renamed in 2016 as «Pacific State University»), which implements an innovative direction on network interaction of educational organizations of the region in the format of a single educational space of the pedagogical cluster, built on the principles of cultural character and personality-oriented education, social partnership and effective information interaction of all participants of the cluster.

In order to implement the mechanisms and forms of continuing pedagogical education in the framework of the requirements of the professional standard «Teacher», which based on the Resource Center of the Pacific State University from 2016 to the present, the regional integration complex «Integration» is being implemented on the problem of developing ethnocultural competence and the linguistic culture of the individual. Let us turn to statistics according to the information of the Ministry of Education and Science in 2017 (Time to study integration, 2019), 1,611 students study at universities (increased by 203 people compared to 2016). Most of them are students from China (955/985); Tajikistan (114/237); Kyrgyzstan (113/145) Uzbekistan (59/103); Azerbaijan (45/36); Ukraine (73/47). In the academic year 2018/2019, 791

children from migrant families studied in the region's schools, and 94 children attended preschool educational institutions. The largest number of children in this category live in the city of Khabarovsk (632 people and 57 people, respectively), the city of Komsomolsk-on-Amur (65/11), and Verkhnebureinsky district (25/7). In other areas, the number of children ranges from 1 to 17 people. All these children need pedagogical and psychological support in organizing educational activities

The model for the implementation of innovative activities of the complex is based on the principles of interaction between institutions of preschool, general, secondary vocational and higher education, including the exchange of experience and the dissemination of best practices for the development of ethnocultural competence and language culture in the territory of the region (Yasvin, 2001). Separately, we note that in the project of innovative activity two strategic directions are implemented for the formation of the language culture of the personality of students. The first direction of the complex is focused on teaching the Russian language as the state language of foreign children in those educational institutions of the region that experience learning difficulties due to poor adaptation to a different cultural environment where there is a difficult development of the Russian language and communication difficulties. The second direction of the complex is aimed at preserving and popularizing native languages, including educational institutions from the villages of the municipal Nikolayevsk-on-Amur and Nanai districts of the Khabarovsk Territory (on the example of the Ulchi and Nanai ethnic groups). In the indicated direction of the project, against the background of the problem of the disappearance of certain languages of representatives of the indigenous peoples of the North, the activity of educational researchers, differing in the principle of high personal conviction about the importance of preserving the native languages of the Amur Region, and, most importantly, in the readiness to create the necessary psychological and pedagogical conditions for the implementation of specific technologies in its conservation. In this context, an important principle is the principle of protecting the educational system of national cultures and traditions in a multicultural state, since it is the educational system that provides a person with knowledge that allows him to integrate into the world of socio-cultural relations, predict the further development of this world and most importantly find his place in it.

Purpose and objectives of the study

Reveal the features of the development of teacher self-government in the cultural and educational space of a multi-ethnic region, on the example of the Khabarovsk Territory.

Literature review

We are in agreement with the opinion of Karabulatova (2006) that in conditions of multi-ethnic contacts of the borderland, an individual, gaining ethnic identity, also acquires a cultural and historical memory, deep historical and cultural roots, a connection with tradition, a sense of historical and intergenerational continuity, continuity and stability (Vyaznikova, 2016; Ignatova, 2009; Soldatova et al., 2018). Against this background, ethnic features, value orientations, principles and stereotypes of behavior of people, representatives of various ethnic communities are formed in the framework of the cultural and educational space. In this regard, the cultural and educational space of a multiethnic region is a condition for the formation and development of ethno specific traits and qualities of a person as a representative of a particular ethnic group. Within its borders, the process of assimilation and translation by the subject of ethno-national and other humanistic values is carried out taking into account regional specifics (Ignatova, 2009).

Practice has shown that the organization of cluster interaction in the cultural and educational space of a multi-ethnic region requires the integration of efforts, first of all teachers, with the developed ability of self-government. Note that in English translation the word «cluster» means «bundle, cruise, group, grow bundles, concentration». On the extent to which the goals of teachers, children, parents will be combined into one, the goals and tasks have been agreed, aspects of personal meaning attractive to all subjects have been found, the success of the strategy developed depends. Under an educational cluster we mean such a system of network interaction of educational organizations, which is aimed at improving the quality of the educational process for the development of priority socio-economic sectors of the region responsible for the efficiency and quality of solving a certain range of tasks at a specific stage of the activities of the actors for the development of the young generation (Karabulatova, 2006).

In this sense, the works of Peisakhov (cited in Kulesh, 2009), who considers self-government in the context of the ability of man to predict the future results of his activities, to define long-range goals and plan his actions and actions, to propose criteria for assessing quality for extracting information on the progress of the self-government process and to amend it, are of course creative. It is obvious that the ability of self-government is a process in which the subject himself determines the problem and develops the optimal tactics and strategy of his activity to solve various problems in life, realizing creative style as a kind of author's position. In this sense, training of a new generation of specialists requires effective forms and methods of organization of educational and educational process, which can reveal potential opportunities of students.

Results

Let us turn to the results of the diagnostic study on the method «Ability of self-government of the person» by Peisakhov, which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Average Student Self-Government Abilities

Indicators	NPGT		KhPG		PNU	
	Quantity elections	%	Quantity elections	%	Quantity elections	%
Analysis of contradictions	2	0,8	29	16	25	11,1
Forecasting	24	10,6	25	13,8	22	9,7
Goal setting	32	14,2	2	1,1	34	15,1
Planning	30	13,3	23	12,7	23	10,2
Criterion for evaluation of quality	24	10,6	18	9,9	26	11,5
Decision-making	26	11,5	16	8,8	17	7,5
Self-checking	32	14,2	28	15,4	26	11,5
Correction	27	12	24	13,2	28	12,4
General SGA	28	12,4	16	8,8	24	10,6

The analysis of the obtained indicators of the ability of the individual to self-government, we have found that among students of the industrial-humanitarian college, the least developed indicator is the analysis of contradictions or orientation in the situation, which can indicate the difficulty of students to detect contradictions in external conditions and create a subjective model of the current situation. Among the students studying at the teacher training college, there was a low capacity for targeting, which indicates a weak ability to form models of the desired future and goals, while in the students of the higher education institution, there were found to be within the average values.

Next stage of the study, the question arose of the connection of self-government of students with their cultural intelligence. In our study, we focused on the view of Soldatova et al. (2018), who believes that cultural intelligence is a certain kind of social intelligence that is aimed at a specific social context defined

by some cultural characteristics of the individual. In other words, cultural intelligence can be defined as a person's ability to adapt in a new cultural environment (Karabulatova, 2006). It is important to note that cultural intelligence includes cognitive, metacognitive, motivational, and behavioral components, encompassing major levels of interpersonal interaction and providing an integrative approach to solving cross-cultural situations characterized by complexity, uncertainty, diversity of cultural dimensions, and adaptation to them.

Let us turn to the results of the diagnostic study on the method «Extended scale of cultural intelligence» by Soldatova et al. (2018), presented in Table 2.

Analysis of the results showed that students of the teacher college have no metacognitive indicator of cultural intelligence in the middle range of values, which may indicate that students are not able to reflex about their own ethnicity and cultural affiliation, as well as that it is impossible to predict behavior in a situation of intercultural interaction.

Students of the Industrial-Humanitarian College have been identified with a low level of motivational indicator of cultural intelligence, which may indicate their weak readiness to learn a new culture. In university students, we have identified a lack of cognitive and behavioral component, which may indicate a lack or low level of knowledge of customs, values, norms of human activity in different cultures, as well as a lack of verbal and non-verbal forms of behavior that would be suitable for contact with persons from other cultures.

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Table 2. Average values of cultural intelligence of the students

Indicators	NPGT		KhPG		PNU	
	Quantity elections	%	Quantity elections	%	Quantity elections	%
Motivational CI	1	10	3	21,4	1	20
Cognitive CI	4	40	3	21,4	-	-
Metacognitive CI	2	20	-	-	2	40
Behavioural CI	2	20	7	50	-	-
General CI	1	10	1	7,1	2	40

The results led to the idea of the importance of considering the beliefs of students, as the constantly changing reality leads people to interpret the events to the maintain the stability of the world's surrounding picture and provide the necessary support to achieve a sense of security. To investigate dominant personality beliefs, we used a methodology in adapting Padun and Kotelnikov's «World assumptions scale» (Padun; Kotelnikova, 2008).

In the study, we define basic beliefs as stable perceptions of the individual about the world and about himself, which influence the thinking, emotional states and behavior of the person. This structure is reflected in the five sub-chases and consists of the individual's internal ideas about the world around him, his own self, and the ways in which the self and the world interact. The basic belief of benevolence - the hostility of the world around us reflects the individual's perceptions of a safe opportunity to trust the world around him and is represented by the «benevolence of the world around him». The basic belief about the justice of the world around us represents the individual's beliefs about the principles of the distribution of luck and misfortune and contains two categories: «justice» and «beliefs about control». The basic belief about the value and significance of the own the indicators of two sub-sections of the questionnaire also characterize self: «Self-image» and «luck». Thanks to these dimensions, we find common points of contact between ethnocultural traditions and global cultural values based on a stable spiritual tradition (Vyaznikova, 2016). The results of the diagnostic study according to the method «World assumptions scale» are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Average Student Base Beliefs

Indicators	NPGT		KhPG		PNU	
	Quantity elections	%	Quantity elections	%	Quantity elections	%
Self-image	33	22,2	27	14,4	41	24,7
Benevolence of the world around him	22	14,9	31	16,6	30	18
Justice	33	22,2	28	15	32	19,3
Luck	31	20,9	72	38,5	32	19,3
Beliefs about control	29	19,6	29	15,5	31	18,7

Analysis of the obtained indicators, we have determined that students of the teacher college are dominated by two types of basic beliefs: the first - basic conviction «self-image», the second type of beliefs – «justice»; Students of the Industrial and Humanitarian College predominate the basic belief of «the benevolence of the world around them»; Students of higher education have the belief «self-image».

Further, with the help of correlation analysis on Pearson coefficient, we have revealed the relationship in a group of students of higher education between a metacognitive indicator of cultural intelligence, the ability of the individual to self-government and the basic «the benevolence of the world around them», «self-image» and «luck» ($r = 0.70$), which may indicate a sufficiently high level of awareness and ability to form patterns of interaction with members of other nationalities, as well as the existence of contradictions between their culture and other cultures, as they often prefer to be convinced of the superiority of their culture.

Among students of the teacher college, the relationship between self-government of the individual and motivational cultural intelligence has been identified with such basic beliefs as «the benevolence of the world around them» and «justice» ($r = 0.60$), which indicates the readiness of students to create a model of the current situation and to rely on its permission for favor from the surrounding world when contradictions are detected in the external multicultural environment. In addition, this may indicate that students have the ability to direct their attention to changing the system of self-government of the individual in a multicultural educational environment in order to prevent the formation of discriminatory forms of inter-ethnic relations in the educational space.

Students of the industrial-humanitarian college have shown a middle level of relationship between self-government of the individual, scales of cultural intelligence and basic beliefs «Beliefs about control», the benevolence of the world around them», «luck» ($r = 0,55$), which may indicate the possibility of renouncing one's own ethnic identity when moving towards one's goals.

Discussions

Thus, the results of theoretical and empirical analysis made it possible to determine that there are peculiarities in the relationship of self-government of the person with cultural intelligence of students, the manifestation of which will depend on different content of beliefs in the cultural and educational space of the multi-ethnic region. These characteristics can manifest themselves in relation to members of their own and other ethnic groups, in the presence of social distance and with different levels of readiness to interact with people of different nationalities.

Conclusion

As a result, the professional education of future teachers requires the search for new approaches to the educational process in order to develop the creative potential and sociocultural adaptability of students who are representatives of different cultures within professional educational institutions with a multi-ethnic educational environment.

One of the possible means of developing personal self-government of future teachers in a multicultural educational environment is the implementation of the course of the program "From self-determination to self-government" using the technology of theoretical and training classes (Kulesh, 2011). The content of the course includes the following thematic clusters:

- Self-knowledge unit, which involves the study of the requirements for the teacher, the self-study of the level of competence, the reflection of one's own professional activity, her self-esteem;
- A planning unit consisting of definition of purpose and tasks, development of a self-development program, selection of personal rules of conduct, forms, means, methods and methods of solving tasks in the work on itself;
- Self-monitoring and self-correction unit in intercultural communication includes reflexion of activities involving direct practical activities based on educational institutions of the province, which differ in most cases by the multi-ethnic population of students. As a result, the presented pedagogical system

contributes to the creation of conditions for the development of personal self-government of future teachers at the stages both before university and before postgraduate education.

In summary, it can be concluded that the cultural and educational space of the Khabarovsk Krai demonstrates one of the models of integration of ethnic groups that inhabit this territory and represent a certain cultural significance, which distinguishes this territory from others. In the light of the policy of regionalization of the education system of the province, we have determined that the management of the process of professional self-development is effective if it is based on the principles of social partnership within the educational cluster. This allows creating a kind of educational network, allowing achieving the necessary effect at the expense of specific contribution of each organization to achievement of results, not only for partnership actors but also for educational actors, while maintaining their differences. Because of this partnership, the wider educational needs of students (future educators) will be met by expanding the educational space and allowing for the exchange of resources, as well as participation in research activities in joint projects with other cluster entities.

Results of the diagnostic study carried out to determine the level of development of self-government ability in 1 students (Future teachers) draw attention to the importance of its development, which in turn leads to reflection and clarification of priorities in the content and mechanisms of implementation of the national educational policy, where the teacher becomes the main and indispensable link in the education system, as advanced theories of the national policy cannot fully ensure the effectiveness of the educational process without developing the personal characteristics of the teacher. As a result, the successful performance of various types of activities of the teacher, refracting through his professional-value settings, leads to independence in decision-making and achievement of the set goal, which implies the presence of development to informed self-government, realized in the «authorship» of professional and personal development, which contributes to the exit from a difficult or crisis situation and to the construction of a perspective and realization of own opportunities. The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

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